

Table 1. Root pulling force of hybrids, their parents, and check varieties. 1983 summer.

Hybrid, variety	Root pulling force (kg)
<i>F₁ hybrids</i>	
V20A/IR50	24.05*
V20A/IR54	25.15*
Z97A/IR50	23.98*
Z97A/IR54	25.10*
Z97A/IR2307-247-2-2-3	22.90*
Z97A/IR13420-6-7-3-1	24.95*
Mean	24.36
<i>Parents</i>	
IR50	18.15
IR54	22.95
IR2307-247-2-2-3	17.90
IR13420-6-3-3-1	19.43
V20B	14.95
Z97B	17.15
Mean	18.43
<i>Checks</i>	
CR44-35	17.18
Sita	21.43
Mean	19.31
CD at 5%	1.23

varieties (Table 1). The highest root pulling force of 25.15 kg was for V20A/IR54, followed by 25.10 kg for Z97A/IR54 and 24.95 kg for Z97A/IR13420-6-7-3-1.

All *F₁* hybrids showed positive heterosis, heterobeltiosis, and standard heterosis for root pulling force

(Table 2). Highest heterosis and heterobeltiosis values were observed in V20A/IR50 and maximum standard heterosis value in Z97A/IR13420-6-7-3-1. A strong, deep, and active root system in hybrid rice may also have potential for its adaptation in rainfed uplands and lowlands. *S*

Table 2. Expression of heterosis, heterobeltiosis, and standard heterosis for root pulling force. 1983 summer.

Hybrid	Heterosis (%)	Heterobeltiosis (%)	Standard heterosis (%)
V20A/IR50	44.9	32.5	40.0
V20A/IR54	33.1	9.6	17.4
Z97A/IR50	35.5	32.1	39.6
Z97A/IR54	24.9	9.4	17.1
Z97A/IR2307-247-2-2-3	30.9	27.9	33.3
Z97A/IR13420-6-7-3-1	36.4	28.4	45.2

Isolation of fertility restorers and maintainers for cytoplasmic genetic male sterile line

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Development of hybrid rice is possible only if the effective fertility restorers for cytoplasmic genetic male sterile (CMS) lines are identified or developed.

Isolation of maintainers for CMS lines is necessary for the development of new CMS lines.

We used the Chinese CMS line V20A as common female parent in crosses

List of complete restorers, partial restorers, and maintainers identified for CMS line V20A at Agricultural Research Institute, Patna, India, 1984.

Complete restorers	Partial restorers	Maintainers
CR289-1208	CR407-6-2	ADT30
CR75-93-Mut. 11-4	CR401-7	Bala
IR9703-4-1-3-3-1	CR167-7	CR407-19
IR2307-247-2-2-3	CR157-22-1900	CR200-788-3
Madhu	IR60	Dhaneshwar
	Pusa 205-15-1	Jikoku Sernai
	RP1451-2266-55-22	MR365
	RP732-26-2	Pusa 2-21
		Ramchure

with standard varieties and elite breeding lines. Percent spikelet fertility of *F₁* hybrids was used as fertility index. Lines that restored 80% or more spikelet fertility were classified as

complete restorers, those restoring between 20% and 79% fertility were partial restorers, and those with less than 20% were classified as maintainers (see table). *S*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

OTHER PESTS

Reaction of rice varieties to root nematode *Hirschmanniella* spp. in the field

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Seventeen rice varieties were evaluated for resistance to root nematode. The average initial population of *Hirschmanniella* spp. extracted from soil samples of the experimental field before planting was 145 nematodes/300 cc soil.

Each test variety was seeded and transplanted into 3 rows at 25 × 25-cm spacing, 10 hills/row.

At 60 d after transplanting, the final population of nematodes was extracted from soil taken from around the root zone in the middle row of each variety.

Reaction for each variety was determined by the ratio of final population to initial population. Five varieties showed resistance to

Hirschmanniella spp. in the field: Kao Paung Klang, Kao Paung, Kao Tah Jue, Kao Yaun, and Kao Klang Pee (see table). *ℓ*

Field reaction of rice varieties to *Hirschmanniella* spp. Patumthani Rice Research Center, Thailand.

Variety	Nematodes ^a (no./300 cc soil)	Pf/Pi ^b	Reaction ^c
Kao Paung Klang	224 a	1.54	R
Kao Paung	237 a	1.63	R
Kao Tah Jue	254 a	1.75	R
Kao Yaun	258 ab	1.78	R
Kao Klang Pee	288 ab	1.98	R
RD9	319 a	2.20	I
Tah Lee	322 ab	2.22	I
Mali Thong	351 abc	2.42	I
Kao Tah Ex	390 abc	2.69	I
Tah Chue	438 abc	3.02	I
IR45	530 abc	3.65	I
Kao Nam Kem	579 abc	3.99	I
TN1	707 bc	4.87	I
Kao Kun Na	785 abc	5.41	S
Kao Pla Lai	896 bc	6.17	S
IR26	1012 c	6.97	S
Kao Ko Dew	1524 c	10.50	S

^aAv of 4 replications. ^bPf = final population at 60 d after transplanting, Pi = initial population. ^cBased on Pf/Pi: R = < 2.0, I = 2.1 - 5.0, and S = > 5.0.

discolored seed and induced longitudinal necrosis in sheath and leaves. When inoculated on plants in the boot stage by leaf-clip or stem injection, the same isolates induced sheath blotching and severe grain discoloration without longitudinal necrosis.

Some varieties apparently recovered following inoculation, with leaf symptoms diminishing on new leaves as they emerged. However, even when the boot was symptomless, the panicle emerged with discolored grain, from which the pathogen could be reisolated. Similar cases have been observed in farmers' fields.

Seed from plants showing glume discoloration, washed and incubated on King's B medium, yielded the pathogen. Up to 100% of the seed from affected plants yielded fluorescent bacteria. When discolored seed was planted without prior breaking of dormancy with dry heat, seedlings showed symptoms within 30 d of emergence.

The pathogen also was consistently recovered from symptomless leaves prior to symptom expression. Severely affected seedlings died, but most survived to flowering. Seed

Pest Control and Management DISEASES

Bacterial sheath brown rot (BSBR) in Latin America

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In rice, disease symptoms identical to those of BSBR, caused by *Pseudomonas fuscovaginae*, have been observed in Guatemala, Panama, Colombia, Surinam, Peru, and Brazil for 10 years. Symptoms include 2-5 mm wide longitudinal brown necrosis of the sheath, sometimes extending its full length. In some cases the lesions extend to the leaf margin or midrib, producing a pronounced stripe (see figure). All leaves of a tiller may be affected.

On some varieties, symptoms are more diffuse, resulting in a brown to maroon blotching with no apparent leaf blade symptoms. The sheath margin

often withers. When the flag leaf sheath is affected, water-soaking may occur.

Preemergence and postemergence panicles from affected flag leaf sheaths invariably show substantial glume discoloration with severely discolored often unfilled grains. Panicles may not emerge completely from affected sheaths.

A rod-shaped, multiflagellate (polar) bacterium producing fluorescent pigments on King's B medium was consistently isolated from plants exhibiting these symptoms. Inoculating healthy plants grown from healthy, heat-treated seed with the isolates reproduced the symptoms. Subsequent characterization and pathogenicity tests showed the pathogen to be indistinguishable from *Pseudomonas fuscovaginae*.

When inoculated on 15- and 40-d-old plants, isolates formed longitudinal necrotic lesions, blotched sheaths, and

a) Necrotic stripe symptoms caused by *P. fuscovaginae*. b) Discoloration and necrosis of sheath caused by *P. fuscovaginae*, CIAT, Cali, Colombia. Necrosis extends to the margin of the flag leaf. Note similarity to sheath rot caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (*Acrocyndrium*).